

Microwave-assisted Vilsmeier-Haack formylation of aromatic substrates

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Abstract : A microwave-assisted Vilsmeier-Haack formylation reaction has been studied on various amines, phenols and polynuclear hydrocarbons under solvent free condition that rapidly affords higher yield of products compared to traditional thermal condition.

Keywords : Aromatic compounds, microwave, Vilsmeier-Haack formylation.

Introduction

Vilsmeier-Haack formylation reaction is one of the most versatile methods for the functionalization of aromatics and heteroaromatics^{1,2} and the formylated products are useful due to their manifold applications in carbon-carbon bond forming reactions in organic synthesis such as aldol type reactions, McMurry coupling reactions etc.³⁻⁸. Moreover, the use of formylated polynuclear aromatic and heteroaromatic hydrocarbons as potential synthons in the design of sensors⁹⁻¹¹ and molecular tweezers¹² in molecular recognition is also rapidly increasing in recent years.

It is well known that *N,N*-dimethylformamide on reaction with phosphorus oxychloride forms an active complex *N,N*-dimethylchloromethylenammonium chloride¹³, referred to as Vilsmeier-Haack reagent which has extensive use as formylating reagent in synthetic organic chemistry. This is widely applicable to active substrates such as amines and phenols. Aromatic hydrocarbons and heterocycles which are only much more active than benzene can also be formylated under exhaustive thermal heating condition¹⁴.

Recently, there has been considerable interest in the microwave (MW) irradiation protocol for the rapid synthesis of a variety of organic compounds due to the absorption of microwave energy by polar molecules¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Reduction in reaction times, improved yields and suppression of side products, relative to traditional thermal heating, are the benefits of this emerging technology¹⁸⁻²¹.

In this context, we wish to report herein a facile synthesis of aromatic formylated products of different kinds following the old, versatile Vilsmeier-Haack reaction (Scheme 1).

Ar = Various phenols, amines, polynuclear hydrocarbons as mentioned in Table 1

Scheme 1

In our efforts to functionalize various polynuclear hydrocarbons, polyphenols, phenols and aromatic amines for the construction of molecular receptors in the area of molecular recognition research²²⁻²⁴, we applied and extended the scope of the Vilsmeier-Haack reaction with microwave activation. Here we noticed that the reaction of polynuclear hydrocarbons like anthracene, phenanthrene, pyrene etc. with POCl_3/DMF yielded a moderate to lower amount of their formyl derivatives within very short reaction time compared to thermal heating under solvent free condition. Functionalization via formylation²⁵ of such polynuclear hydrocarbons on microwave irradiation finds an easy, simple route in absence of high boiling solvents. Various phenols, amines as cited in Table 1²⁶, also undergo smooth reaction leading to the desired formylated products with moderate to high yields. In the reactions, catalytic use of tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB) did not affect the yield in many cases but reduces the reaction time probably due to *in situ* formation of activated *N,N*-dimethylbromomethylenammonium salt. Aromatic phenols

Table 1. Reactions with POCl₃/DMF under microwave irradiation

Substrates	Products	Microwave condition time, yield (%)	Thermal condition using 1,2-dichlorobenzene as solvent, time, yield (%)
	1 min (600 W), 60	2 h, 58	
	3 min (600 W), 50	8 h, 20-25	
	5 min (600 W), 70	24 h, 0	
	5 min (600 W), di = 20, mono = 60, tri = 20	30 h, mono = 0, di = 40, tri = 6	
	+ mono (4b) + triformylated (4c) products		
	5 min (600 W), 75-80	24 h, 0	
	3 min (450 W), 70-75	3 h, 50	
	3 min (600 W), 95	9 h, 82	
	10 min (600 W), <i>ortho</i> = 10-15, <i>para</i> = 0	24 h, 0	
	3 min (450 W), 60	9 h, 25	
	3 min (600 W), mono = 85, di = 10-15	4 h, mono = 45, di = 5-10	
	5 min (600 W), 80	6 h, 40, 80-84 ²⁷	
	5 min (300 W), 60	16 h, 0	

having one -OH group are difficult to formylate under microwave irradiation whereas phenols with more than one -OH group such as catechol, resorcinol etc. are more reactive under the same reaction conditions to give desired formylated products. The presence of TBAB in such cases increases the yield marginally and reduces the reaction time as well. However, in contrary the protected phenols (as ether) are found to exhibit higher yield within short reaction time by following the use of lower pulse (300 to 450 W). In contrast, polynuclear hydrocarbons bring better results in the use of higher pulse (600 W). Anthrone under similar reaction condition gives chloro-aldehyde in excellent yield within 4–5 min and rate is also marginally accelerated in presence of TBAB. The same reaction under thermal condition did not produce any result on 24 h. The substrate *N,N*-dimethylaniline being electronically rich leads to 4-*N,N*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde, another fluorescent molecule of interest in bioorganic chemistry, in 80% yield. To broaden the scope of such easy methodology, toluene was also considered (excluded from Table 1) for the formation of 4-methylbenzaldehyde (b.p. 80 °C). We isolated the compound (matches TLC with authentic sample) in lesser amount since maximum amount escapes from the reaction vessel during the reaction.

One representative reaction procedure : To a mixture of POCl₃ (0.98 mmol) and dimethylformamide (1.5 mmol) in a conical flask anthracene **1** (0.56 mmol) was added and the open mouth was covered by cotton. The mixture was next irradiated at 600 W with a domestic microwave oven for an optimum time of 1 min. The residue after neutralization with saturated NaHCO₃ was extracted with ethyl acetate. After removal of the solvent the product **1a**, mixed with little amount of starting material **1**, was purified by column chromatography (ethyl acetate : pet ether = 1 : 4) and was isolated in 60% yield as yellowish solid (m.p. lit. 104 °C, found 101–103 °C). The same reaction was performed under identical condition in presence of catalytic amount of tetrabutylammonium bromide.

In conclusion, we have thus revisited the well known Vilsmeier-Haack reaction under microwave irradiation and established a very simple technique for the preparation of various formylated polynuclear hydrocarbons, aromatic amines and phenols by simple mixing the reactants without using halogenated solvents (e.g. 1,2-dichlorobenzene). The notable advantages offered by this technique are the

reduced reaction times, high purity and relatively better yield of products compared to conventional thermal condition.

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